

ν_{C-O} at $\sim 1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$. A sharp band at $\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($C=N$) of the Schiff base indicated bonding through azomethine nitrogen. Thus keto $\rightleftharpoons$ thioenol tautomerism of the Schiff base in alkaline medium and subsequent coordination to the metal ion by deprotonation of SH group are evident by the absence of ν_{SH} bands in the region $2800-2650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the complexes⁵. This is further supported by a new band appearing at 660 cm^{-1} ($C-S$)^{6,7}. An additional band due to $\nu_{C=N}$ (formed by thioenolisation of Schiff base) appearing at $\sim 1480\text{ cm}^{-1}$ confirms the thioenol coordination of the ligand. The above facts clearly indicate that the ligand salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone behaves as a bidentate tridentate ($\bar{O}, N, S$) ligand. Charles *et al.*⁸ observed ν_{C-O} at 1120 cm^{-1} in several oxine complexes of metals, the position of band slightly varying with the metal. In the present work, the appearance of a strong band at $\sim 1120\text{ cm}^{-1}$ clearly indicates the presence of oxine group coordinating through nitrogen and oxygen atoms as unidentate bidentate ligand^{9,10}. The presence of coordinated water molecule in the aqua-complex $[Cr(stsc)(ox)(H_2O)]$ was indicated by the bands at 3400 and 830 cm^{-1} . However, these bands due to water molecule are absent and new bands are observed in the complexes containing monodentate ligands. One of the bands of $\nu_{C=C} + \nu_{C=N}$ at $\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to pyridine, γ -picoline and isoquinoline was found to overlap with the band of salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone whereas the other one was found at $\sim 1550\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This suggests the coordination of these ligands through nitrogen atom¹¹. A negative shift of $20-25\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in ν_{C-O} in the urea complex indicates that urea is coordinated through oxygen atom to the metal ion¹² ($\sim 1660\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in free ligand). The ν_{P-O} band observed at 1070 cm^{-1} for triphenylphosphine oxide indicates participation of its oxygen atom in coordination¹³ (1195 cm^{-1} in free ligand). A negative shift of $20-25\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in $\nu_{C=S}$ in the thio-urea complex indicates that thiourea is coordinated through sulphur atom to the metal ion¹⁴ (685 cm^{-1} in free ligand). The presence of $Cr-O$ and $Cr-N$ bonds was evident from the ν_{Cr-O} and ν_{Cr-N} bands appearing at ~ 410 and $\sim 470\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively.

The electronic spectra of the complexes exhibit two bands in the region $18500-19200$ and $23200-23400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. These can be assigned to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ transitions, respectively, which are typical of octahedral coordination¹⁵. Room temperature (298 K) magnetic moment values around $3.79-3.85\text{ B.M.}$ for these complexes suggest their spin-free nature.

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Some Complexes of Copper with Thiosalicylic Acid

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THE reactions of thioglycolic acid with Cu^{II} were first studied by Bjerrum¹ who found that Cu^{II} catalyses the oxidation of thioglycolic acid and used it as a basis for the microdetermination of copper. A complex with 1 : 1 molar ratio is formed when $CuCl_2$ and mercaptoacetic acid react at 10° in ethanol. Earlier work on the Cu^{II} -thiosalicylic acid (TAS) system is only sparse and deals mostly with analytical aspects²⁻⁴.

Experimental

$CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ thiosalicylic acid (TSA), and all the other reagents were of AnalaR grade.

$Cu^I(SC_6H_4COOH)$ (1) : $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ (2.49 g, 0.01 mol) was dissolved in 0.05 M H_2SO_4 and mixed with a solution of TSA (3.06 g, 0.02 mol) dissolved in $NH_3 - NH_4Cl$ (0.025 M). The resulting colourless solution was acidified with dilute H_2SO_4 upto the final concentration of 0.05 M. All operations were done in the absence of air. The precipitated colourless complex (1) was filtered and kept under reduced pressure (Found: Cu, 29.30; total S, 14.80; mercaptide S, 14.80. $Cu^I(SC_6H_4COOH)$ requires: Cu, 29.29; total S, mercaptide S, 14.75%).

$Cu^{II}(HSC_6H_4COOH)_2SO_4$ (2) : $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ (2.49 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in 2 M H_2SO_4 was mixed with TSA (3.06 g, 0.02 mol) dissolved in $NH_3 - NH_4Cl$ (0.025 M). A sparingly soluble precipitated deep blue complex (2) was filtered and kept under reduced pressure (Found: Cu, 13.58; total S, 20.50; mercaptide S, 13.70; sulphate S, 6.80. $Cu^{II}(HSC_6H_4COOH)_2SO_4$ requires: Cu, 13.57; total S, 20.47, mercaptide S, 13.65; sulphate S, 6.84%).

Results and Discussion

The colourless compound (1) readily transforms to an intensely blue product on exposure to air most presumably due to the oxidation of Cu^I to Cu^{II} . The blue compound (2) undergoes slow decomposition if kept in contact with the mother liquor. The ν_{S-H} band occurring at 2560 cm^{-1} for TSA was absent in the ir spectra of the complexes 1 and 2, suggesting SH coordination. The $\nu_{C=O}$ band at 1650 cm^{-1} remained unaltered, which indicates that carbonyl group was not involved in coordination.

In case of the Cu^{II} complex 2, the ir spectrum showed the presence of SO_4^{2-} bands at 1100 cm^{-1} . It is difficult to draw conclusions from the ir spectrum about the bonding arrangement around Cu^{II} . The intense blue colour of the complex, however, strongly suggests a charge transfer absorption characteristic of SH coordination since neither the SO_4^{2-} ion nor the COOH group alone or together can give such high absorptions. They are characteristic of Cu^{II} -thiolatocarboxylate complexes such as with thioglycolic acid, α -mercaptopropionic acid and thiomalic acid.

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Ternary Complexes of Nickel(II) with 2,2'-Bipyridyl or Histidine as Primary Ligand and Glycollic, Lactic, Malic and the corresponding Amino Acids as Secondary Ligands

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FORMATION constants of some hydroxy and the corresponding amino acid complexes of Ni^{II} having 2,2'-bipyridyl or histidine as the primary ligand have been determined in aqueous solution using modified form of Irving-Rossotti titration techniques¹. Amino acids form stronger chelates than the corresponding hydroxy acids.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. Nickel perchlorate, sodium hydroxide and perchloric acid solutions were standardised by complexometric² and acid-base³ methods. For each system five sets of the solutions each of initial volume 50.00 ml having an ionic strength $I=0.2\text{ M}$ ($NaClO_4$) were pH-metrically titrated against standard NaOH

Fig. 1. pH titrations curves for the Ni^{II} -histidine-glycine system at 30° , $I=0.2\text{ M}$ ($NaClO_4$): (1) $0.02\text{ M HClO}_4 + 0.002\text{ M histidine} + 0.178\text{ M NaClO}_4$, (2) $0.022\text{ M HClO}_4 + 0.178\text{ M NaClO}_4$, (3) $0.02\text{ M HClO}_4 + 0.002\text{ M histidine} + 0.002\text{ M Ni(ClO}_4)_2 + 0.176\text{ M NaClO}_4$, (4) $0.022\text{ M HClO}_4 + 0.002\text{ M glycine} + 0.176\text{ M NaClO}_4$ and (5) $0.02\text{ M HClO}_4 + 0.002\text{ M histidine} + 0.002\text{ M glycine} + 0.002\text{ M Ni(ClO}_4)_2 + 0.174\text{ M NaClO}_4$; initial volume = 50 ml, $[NaOH]=0.2\text{ M}$.